

EMPLOYABILITY OF TOURISM GRADUATES: A CASE STUDY OF HANOI UNIVERSITY, VIETNAM (PART 2: FINDINGS FROM THE INITIAL INTER- VIEW SURVEY)

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

The tourism and travel industry, which generated 334 million jobs in 2019, contributed to one-fourth of global new jobs, but its contribution to the total travel and tourism GDP decreased from 10.4% to 5.5% (WTTC, 2021; ILO, 2020). Vietnam is one of the top 10 places where tourism is growing fastest in the world, with more than 18.008 million international tourists and 85 million domestic tourists coming to the country. As of December 2019, the country boasted 2,648 international travel agencies, 26,864 tour guides, and 30,000 accommodation establishments, accommodating 650,000 rooms (Hanh, 2021). The demand for human resources in the industry continues to grow, but the supply of qualified workers has not kept pace. Little study interest has been shown in the broader knowledge of employability, including the views of tourism graduates (McQuaid & Lindsay, 2005; Eldeen et al., 2018; Eurico et al., 2015). Dhaliwal & Misra (2020) suggest further research on the impact of personal attributes, such as motivation, self-efficacy, and personality traits, on employability. Future research could investigate the interactions between personal attributes and other determinants of employability, such as education and work experience, which could offer valuable insights into enhancing employability among graduates. Future studies might investigate strategies to increase the beneficial effects of informal learning by enhancing cooperation between employers and universities. Furthermore, Benbow and Hora (2018) proposed that future research should employ field research methods that focus on occupation- and discipline-specific perspectives of valuable skills, in order to investigate how cultural models influence various competencies and their application in various employment fields. We recommend further research to investigate how external factors, such as industry trends and economic conditions, influence employability and how universities can prepare graduates for a successful career without compromising the quality of academic courses (Cheng et al.,

2022; Sato et al., 2021).

Tourism management training programs taught at universities in Vietnam can assist students in developing solid fundamental knowledge. However, these training courses are limited in their ability to enhance the employability skills of graduates. While firms expect applicants with soft skills in addition to technical expertise, a significant number of tourism management courses do not emphasize interpersonal skills (Nga, 2021). Universities face challenges in developing networks with industry collaborators and engaging them in school training practices due to their distinct objectives and priorities. Finding common ground and coordinating interests can be challenging. Limited resources, such as time, money, and personnel, can hinder effective partnerships. Additionally, universities often adhere to academic schedules that may conflict with industry demands, making it difficult to coordinate schedules and balance academic obligations with industry demands (Hong, 2023; Lanh, 2021). Hanoi University's tourism lecturers argue that classroom-based teaching methods, such as lectures and tutoring, have shortcomings in enhancing graduates' employability. Classrooms cover a wide range of topics, limiting practical training sessions and hands-on learning opportunities. They also lack the resources and technology available in workplaces, limiting the authenticity and strain of real-world professional environments and hindering competencies like decision-making under pressure (Dung, N.P., Giang, K.Y., personal communications, June 10, 2023).

The current DBA study focuses on the professionalism and employability of tourism graduates, highlighting the importance of these concepts in bridging the gap between the industry's need for skilled workers and the higher education system's capacity to provide them. The study explores the viewpoints of the tourism industry, universities (specifically Hanoi University, where the author currently works), and recent graduates, with a particular focus on the employability and professionalism of tourism graduates. This research topic is of particular interest as it contributes to the expanding body of knowledge on the employability of graduates in the tourism industry.

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

This DBA study aims to address the three research questions as follows:

1. What professional and personal competencies are considered essential for employability in Vietnam's tourism industry?
2. How can Hanoi University strengthen its informal learning and training practices for enhancing the employability of their tourism management students?
3. How can Hanoi University modify their tourism training programs to accommodate the diverse demands of tourism industry employers?

The study will employ **qualitative research methods**, including narrative inquiry, semi-structured and in-depth interviews, content analysis of secondary doc-

uments, and case study strategies, to investigate employability in Vietnam's tourism industries. It will investigate strategies for improving informal learning practices in Hanoi University's bachelor's program and recommend changes to meet employers' needs. We will conduct **in-depth interviews** with 30–40 fresh graduates, university lecturers, and industry experts. This sample size is determined as manageable and generally sufficient to reach the maturation point “when no more new issues are identified, data begin to repeat with no added understanding of the issues, and so further data collection becomes redundant” (Hennink et al., 2020; Morse, 1994; Starks & Trinidad, 2007). A combination of primary and secondary data sources contributes to the robustness of the study through triangulation (Leech, 2007). According to Krippendorff (2004, p. 18), **content analysis** is a research technique that provides replicable and valid inferences from texts or other meaningful matters in their contexts. It involves specialized procedures and is learnable, independent of researcher authority. Content analysis is a scientific tool that should yield replicable findings and valid results, allowing for scrutiny and upholding claims despite independently available evidence. This **case study**, which aims to provide inferences for interpretation, argumentation, and generalization of findings from in-depth interviews, will gather secondary data for content analysis from various sources. These sources include international organizations, government or industry associations' publications and working documents (e.g., VNAT's handbook on measuring tourism employment in Viet Nam, MOTIVE Vietnam graduates' employment monitoring project's publications), official websites of tourism universities and colleges in Viet Nam, Hanoi University's publications on alumni, and industry surveys on the employment of tourism graduates.

We analyze the data thematically in accordance with the **three research questions** to identify the competencies required for employability in the industry, develop a comprehensive framework of both professional and personal competencies, determine effective strategies for enhancing informal learning, and identify necessary modifications to the undergraduate tourism training programs at Hanoi University. **Thematic analysis** is a method of studying patterns within data to uncover meaning. It involves analyzing patterns and themes within the data set, focusing on key aspects related to the research questions. There are **two main coding approaches: inductive (data-driven) and deductive (theory-driven)** (Miles, 2014; Kuckartz, 2014; Merriam, 2016; Vanover et al., 2021). The deductive approach in this study initially determines a set of codes that include a comprehensive employability framework (professional and personal competencies), employability, informal learning strategies (experiential learning, work-integrated learning, internships and apprenticeships), personal factors, work environment conditions, and the university's informal learning policies. This study adopts a **three-perspective approach**, and it's crucial to note that the inductive approach may lead to the emergence of additional codes as new themes or patterns emerge.

Strauss and Corbin (1990) assert that the **grounded theory method**, which consists of open (or initial), axial, and theoretical coding strategies, can analyze qualitative data to generate theories grounded in the data itself. **Initial coding** splits qualitative data and evaluates and compares them for similarities and differences. Most qualitative research, especially grounded theory and studies involving a range of data types such as interview transcripts, can use initial coding (Saldana, 2016, p. 115). In the first round, the author will employ the open coding strategy to get as many codes as possible. **Axial coding** is a method that reassembles data fragmented during initial coding, identifying dominant and less important codes. It involves crossing out synonyms, removing redundant codes, and selecting the best representative ones. First cycle coding identifies the "axis" of axial coding, which links categories with subcategories and specifies properties and dimensions. This method helps researchers understand the contexts, conditions, interactions, and consequences of a process (Saldana, 2016, p. 244). In the second round, the author will explore interrelationships between categories and subcategories as well as emerging themes. According to Saldana (2016, p. 199), a theme, an outcome of categorization and analytic reflection of codes, is an extended phrase or sentence that identifies what a unit of data is about and/or what it means. Furthermore, the author develops **narrative stories** that connect categories based on direct quotes from participants. The author uses theoretical coding, a grounded theory analysis method, in the third round of coding to integrate various categories and concepts around a central or core category, thereby identifying the primary theme of the research. The **theoretical code** is not the theory itself but an abstraction that models the integration (Saldana, 2016, p. 250). We will utilize qualitative data analysis software like Nvivo or Atlas.Ti to arrange and display codes and categories, pinpoint themes within the data, and build a comprehensive framework for graduate employability.

According to Blaxter et al. (2010), **interpretation** refers to the process of interpreting the data you have collected and analyzed, and then comparing your interpretation with those of others. Interpretation involves identifying and describing 'patterns' or trends observed in the data, as well as explaining the reasons behind these patterns. Characterizing the broader contexts and dimensions surrounding employability in the Vietnam tourism industry requires a detailed description. Hillocks (2010) argued that **argumentation** is "at the heart of critical thinking and academic discourse, the kind of writing students need to know." Argumentation is a crucial cognitive ability for dealing with contradictory information, perspectives, opinions, etc. An argument entails establishing a claim and then proving it using logical reasoning supported by verifiable examples and facts (Besnard et al., 2014; Toulmin, 2003). Using Toulmin's model, the author of this DBA study can structure discussion of the research findings in a clear, logical, and persuasive manner. The research methodology employed in this DBA study can be depicted in Figure 1 on the next page.

FINDINGS

At this stage of the study, the author has successfully conducted semi-structured in-depth interviews with a total of 10 respondents from each of the three interviewed groups. The preliminary data analysis has begun, focusing on the interview transcripts of the two representatives from each group (coded as LEC1, LEC2 for the university lecturers; EMP1, EMP2 for the industry employers and GRA1, GRA2 for the tourism fresh graduates).

After the first round of data analysis (employing the initial or open coding techniques), the author finds 28 code groups from the two interview transcripts with fresh tourism graduates and categorizes them under three main themes: university training program, employment capacity and informal learning. A parallel analysis of the second group of university lecturers reveals a total of 13 code groups, while the analysis of the third group of tourism industry experts produces 15 code groups. In addition, the author includes one to three direct quotations from the respondents to illustrate these codes.

In the second round of data analysis (known as the axial coding), the author compares and contrasts the three perspectives to examine how these categories interacted, influenced each other, and influenced the three main themes.

Figure 1. The Research Methodology

In the first theme of Employability Competencies, a new category “Importance of work attitude” emerges, comprising of two codes, including “Professional attitudes” and “Work attitudes”. Soft skills and positive attitudes developed through

training and informal learning programs, such as mentorship, can increase employability. Both graduates and industry experts say about the work attitudes in a similar manner, for example:

"When working in any environment, you have to do your job well" (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024);

"If you think positively, it will show in your face and communication" (EMP1, personal communication, July 9, 2024);

"Attitude is one of the most important factors" (EMP2, personal communication, July 12, 2024).

However, the three groups have quite different opinions about two codes: "Soft skills" and "Probationary assessment". While graduates tend to underscore soft skill "I can develop my English presentation skills and speaking in public" (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024), university lecturers balance both professional skills and soft skills "In terms of employability, vocational skills and soft skills are the deciding factors" (LEC1, personal communication, July 1, 2024), and industry experts highly evaluate it "One of the very important requirements for personnel in the tourism sector is listening, speaking, reading, and writing foreign languages" (EMP2, personal communication, July 12, 2024). While university training programs provide the necessary knowledge, informal learning helps students develop soft skills in real-world environments. Furthermore, university lecturers emphasize the role of probationary assessment "Probationary assessment is an important step in determining the ability and potential of new employees". In contrast, industry experts refer to the final results "We will evaluate employees on probation after completing this 2-month journey".

In the second theme of University Training Programs, a category "Methods of teaching and training" is newly developed from the two codes "Teaching methods and supports from university" and "Active methods of teaching and learning". Active teaching methods not only equip students with knowledge, but they also encourage them to participate in informal learning activities, thereby improving employability. The three groups mention various pedagogical approaches to enhance the effectiveness of training and learning experiences of students:

"We will visit companies, hotels, and travel agencies to learn about their environment" (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024);

"Do not let students learn passively" (LEC2, personal communication, July 5, 2024);

"There will be a constant emphasis on professional training as well as advanced training" (EMP2, personal communication, July 12, 2024).

On the other hand, there is a slight difference when the groups talk about the specifics of the code “Undergraduate tourism curriculum”. Graduates mention the major they studied in their curriculum “I studied at Hanoi University, majoring in tourism and travel services management, and graduated with honors” (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024), whereas lecturers point out internationalization of the training program “Highly internationalized, not just foreign language training” (LEC1, personal communication, July 1, 2024).

In the third theme of Informal Learning, all groups face the code “Difficulties in studying and practicing”. Internship and mentorship experiences can affect students' work attitudes and employability. Graduates disclose managing an internship and writing a CV can be challenging “In fact, at HANU when I was studying, I did not learn CV writing skills” (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024). Lecturers state difficulties and challenges in learning “There are so many deadlines that students feel like they don’t have enough time.” (LEC1, personal communication, July 1, 2024). Similarly, industry experts draw attention to difficulty in integrating and understanding the working environment “You need to have the capacity to be able to integrate” (EMP2, personal communication, July 12, 2024).

With regard to the category “Support and mentorship”, despite the fact that tourism fresh graduates emphasize the support and mentorship provided by colleagues, the other groups do not specifically mention this aspect. Industry experts refer to on-the-job training but did not elaborate on mentorship, for example:

“Agoda has a mentor system, which means that people who have done it before will mentor the new people.” (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024);

“Internship programs are essential for you to adapt and experience the working environment.” (LEC1, personal communication, July 1, 2024).

As a final step in the data analysis process, the author constructed stories that illustrated how the categories within the three themes interacted and contributed to the goal of improving the employability of new tourism graduates, which was linked to your three research questions. The main results were as follows:

Story 1: Professional and personal competencies required in the tourism industry In Vietnam, to succeed in the tourism industry, new graduates need to possess a range of professional and personal competencies. Soft skills are one of the important factors. As one graduate shared: “I will be able to develop my English presentation skills and present in front of many people.” (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024).

The lecturer also highlighted the importance of work attitude. One lecturer emphasized that: “If you think positively, it will show in your face and communication.” (EMP1, personal communication, July 9, 2024).

The combination of soft skills and a positive attitude not only helps students stand out in the eyes of employers but also increases their adaptability in the diverse working environment of the tourism industry.

Story 2: Adjusting training programs to meet recruitment needs

Hanoi University needs to appropriately adjust its training program to meet the diverse needs of employers. A bachelor said: "I studied at Hanoi University, majoring in tourism and travel services management, and graduated with honors." (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024). However, students also realized that: "In fact, at HANU when I was studying, I did not learn CV writing skills." (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024). This suggests that there is a need for more courses on CV writing and interview skills to better prepare students for the job search process. In addition, lecturers also said: "There is a need to internationalize the training program, not just train in foreign languages." (LEC1, personal communication, July 1, 2024). Adjusting the curriculum to combine theory and practice will help students be more prepared for the real needs of the industry.

Story 3: Improving informal training

Hanoi University also needs to focus on improving informal training to enhance the employability of new graduates. One graduate emphasized that: "Those extracurricular activities will give me soft skills and real-world experiences." (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024). Mentorship also plays an important role in career development. Specifically, graduates said: "Agoda has a mentor system, which means that people who have done it before will mentor the new people." (GRA1, personal communication, July 18, 2024). We need to expand internship programs and industry partnerships to provide students more opportunities for hands-on experience and networking with employers. As one lecturer stated: "Internship programs are essential for you to adapt and experience the working environment." (LEC1, personal communication, July 1, 2024).

ORIGINALITY AND VALUE

The qualitative data analysis from the interviews provides insights into the competencies required of new tourism graduates in Vietnam. The perspectives from students, lecturers, and industry experts not only reflect the diversity of experiences but also create a holistic picture of the labor market. The stories illustrate how interactive categories demonstrate originality in approach and analysis, allowing readers to better understand the current state and needs of the industry.

The research results can be reliable and genuine for various reasons. First, the results reflect views from a variety of respondents (graduates, lecturers, profes-

sionals), ensuring that there is no single perspective, thereby creating a comprehensive and fair view of the situation. We collect data from a variety of sources, avoiding bias towards any particular group. This helps provide a fair view of different aspects of recruitment capacity. Second, direct quotations from participants help ensure the authenticity of the data, allowing readers to get a better sense of the realities that graduates and faculty are experiencing. Fourth, the closely linked codes and categories derived from the interviews demonstrated consistency in the findings. Furthermore, the systematic execution of the analysis process bolstered the reliability of the results.

The study results are not only of academic value, but also of practical value, providing useful information for training program managers and employers in developing appropriate training programs. The value of these findings also lies in their ability to generate concrete recommendations for Hanoi University and other educational institutions to improve their informal learning and training programs.

While the initial analysis provides valuable insights, the current paper faces several limitations that impede the study's significant implications, including small sample size, lacking content analysis of secondary documents, or limited geographical scope of Hanoi University. To address the shortcoming and limitations, the following research activities are proposed to undertake in the next stage of the DBA study:

- Collect data from a larger sample of 10–15 graduates from different institutions, about 10 tourism lecturers, and about 10 tourism industry professionals to get a broader view of the needs and required competencies, as well as the possibilities for cooperation between training institutions and tourism businesses in advancing informal training activities.
- Analyze additional data to enrich initial findings to uncover new themes and patterns, use qualitative analysis methods.
- Identify similarities and differences, compare new findings with previous research and related theory, thereby clarifying the research's value.
- Analyze the implications of the findings for training program administrators, employers, and educational policy. Identify the practical applications of the results.
- Provide specific recommendations for Hanoi University on improving training programs and student support.
- Suggest future research paths that will enhance the academic contributions and practical applications of the study's findings.

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